

NEW DATA ON TERRESTRIAL TARDIGRADES OF THE MARITIME ANTARCTIC

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Antarctic soils and scarce vegetation host communities of small invertebrates, such as mites, springtails, insects, rotifers, nematodes, and tardigrades, which are able to survive in extreme conditions. These communities have been repeatedly explored during the last century. However, due to their difficult accessibility, some regions of the Antarctic remain understudied. Besides, the recent progress in integrative taxonomy urges reinvestigating the search for hidden diversity.

Current research focuses on terrestrial Tardigrada (i.e., tardigrades inhabiting water films in terrestrial habitats). To obtain the tardigrade moss and algae samples, they were collected during the 28th Ukrainian Antarctic Expedition from December 2023 to April 2024 and delivered to Ukraine for investigation. Altogether, 70 samples were taken from various locations on the western coast of the Antarctic Peninsula and the neighboring islands (mainly from the Wilhelm Archipelago and the South Shetland Islands). Tardigrades and their eggs were extracted from the samples, put on the permanent slides, studied using light microscopy (PCM), and identified using keys and species descriptions.

The investigation revealed the presence of both heterotardigrade and eutardigrade species, with *Mesobiotus* spp. and *Diphascion* spp. being the most abundant in the samples. A taxonomic account of the tardigrades found is given. Possible relationships of tardigrades to habitat parameters and perspectives of further research are discussed. Special attention is given to ciliate symphorionts (*Propyxidium* sp.) of tardigrades from the Antarctic.